

International Journal of Medical Informatics

Computer-Aided Intra-Operatory Positioning of an MRgHIFU Applicator dedicated to Abdominal Thermal Therapy using Particle Swarm Optimization

--Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	
Article Type:	Research paper
Keywords:	Particle swarm optimization; computer-aided positioning; HIFU transducer, thermal therapy; near field safety
Corresponding Author:	Orane Lorton University of Geneva Faculty of Medicine SWITZERLAND
First Author:	Yacine M'Rad
Order of Authors:	Yacine M'Rad Caecilia Charbonnier Marcelo Elias de Oliveira, MSc Pauline Coralie Guillemin Lindsey Alexandra Crowe Thibaud Kössler Pierre-Alexandre Poletti Sana Boudabbous Alexis Ricoeur Rares Salomir Orane Lorton
Abstract:	This paper presents a novel software tool developed to optimize the positioning of a high intensity focused ultrasound transducer (HIFU) dedicated to abdominal thermal therapy. The software employs particle swarm optimization (PSO) to determine the optimal transducer position, thereby maximizing the efficacy of the treatment while minimizing the near field risk. Magnetic resonance imaging data from in vivo HIFU ablation in pig livers was used for ground truth comparison. The numerical results were consistent with the in vivo test-case scenarios. The method demonstrated to be robust and time effective. The manual segmentation of anatomic structures was time-consuming, indicating a direction for future improvements.
Suggested Reviewers:	Benoit Larrat benoit.larrat@cea.fr Rajiv Chopra Rajiv.Chopra@utsouthwestern.edu

1 **Computer-Aided Intra-Operatory Positioning of an MRgHIFU Applicator** 2 **dedicated to Abdominal Thermal Therapy using Particle Swarm Optimization**

3 Yacine M'Rad³, Caecilia Charbonnier^{1,2}, Marcelo Elias de Oliveira², Pauline Coralie Guillemain¹, Lindsey
4 Alexandra Crowe³, Thibaud Kössler⁴, Pierre-Alexandre Poletti³, Sana Boudabbous^{1,3}, Alexis Ricoeur^{1,3}, Rares
5 Salomir^{1,3}, Orane Lorton¹

6 ¹Image Guided Interventions Laboratory (GR-949), Faculty of Medicine, University of Geneva, Geneva,
7 Switzerland

8 ²Artanim, Medical Research Department, Geneva, Switzerland

9 ³Radiology Division, University Hospitals of Geneva, Geneva, Switzerland

10 ⁴Oncology Department, University Hospitals of Geneva, Geneva, Switzerland

11 **Correspondence:**

12 Orane Lorton

13 Rue Gabrielle Perret Gentil, 4

14 1205 Geneva

15 Tel: +41 22 37 25 215

16 Email: orane.lorton@unige.ch

17

18 **Abstract**

19 This paper presents a novel software tool developed to optimize the positioning of a high intensity focused
20 ultrasound transducer (HIFU) dedicated to abdominal thermal therapy. The software employs particle swarm
21 optimization (PSO) to determine the optimal transducer position, thereby maximizing the efficacy of the
22 treatment while minimizing the near field risk. Magnetic resonance imaging data from *in vivo* HIFU ablation in
23 pig livers was used for ground truth comparison. The numerical results were consistent with the *in vivo* test-
24 case scenarios. The method demonstrated to be robust and time effective. The manual segmentation of anatomic
25 structures was time-consuming, indicating a direction for future improvements.

26

27 **Abbreviations** ARC, average reflection coefficient; CAD, computer-aided design; DoF, degrees of freedom;
28 EP, experimental position; GUI, graphical user interface; HIFU, high intensity focused ultrasound; ITK, insight
29 toolkit; MRgHIFU, magnetic resonance guided high intensity focused ultrasound; MRI, magnetic resonance
30 imaging; PSO, particle swarm optimization; RAM, random access memory; ROI, region of interest; TOP,
31 theoretical optimal position.

32 **Keywords (3-6)**

33 Particle swarm optimization, computer-aided positioning, HIFU transducer, thermal therapy, near field safety

34 1. INTRODUCTION

35 High-intensity focused ultrasound (HIFU) is a non-invasive ablation technique for the treatment of solid tumors.
36 Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is an advanced tool used for therapeutic ultrasound guidance providing near
37 real-time temperature monitoring and high-resolution 3D anatomical images [1-4]. The feasibility and
38 efficiency of magnetic resonance guided HIFU (MRgHIFU) have been demonstrated and widely accepted in
39 the treatment of uterine fibroids, prostate cancer and bone metastases [5-12]. MRgHIFU ablation in the liver is
40 very promising for the treatment of secondary cancer as more than 80% of the metastatic colorectal cancers are
41 surgically ineligible [13, 14]. However, HIFU lesioning in the liver is very challenging due to the presence of
42 critical surrounding organs such as bones, lungs or stomach. Ultrasound propagation through tissues with
43 significant impedance change is subject to undesirable effects at interfaces, including absorption, reflections,
44 standing waves, and focal point shift. The critical presence of the air in the lungs, stomach or bowel acts as
45 strong ultrasound reflector, and may induce damages on the transducer itself or in unexpected anatomic areas
46 inside the body. Major vessels close to the target also need to be considered as the blood flow cools down the
47 vicinity of the vessel wall, named the heat sink effect. This requires application of higher emitted energy to
48 compensate for the losses, increasing the risk of heating in undesirable areas, the risk of damaging the vessels
49 and even inducing local hemorrhage via transient cavitation. In addition, focusing through the rib cage is
50 challenging due to the ultrasound distortions and scattering that lead to losses in the energy deposition at the
51 focal point. The higher energy absorption rate of the bone, approximately a factor of 12 compared to the soft
52 tissues [15] may induce substantial heating in the near field and may even propagate into skin burns or
53 infiltrating thermal lesions [16-18].

54 In 2014, Napoli et al. [19] reported a successful non-invasive treatment of a hepatocellular carcinoma by
55 MRgHIFU, but they highlighted the limitations induced by the presence of the rib cage. Several solutions have
56 been proposed to manage the rib cage issue, including partial rib resection before the HIFU intervention [20,
57 21]. This surgical solution is in flagrant contradiction with the minimally-invasive nature of the intervention but
58 offers a solution when no other treatments are practicable. Another approach was the development of software
59 method such as de-activation of the transducer's elements located in front of the ribs, reducing the energy
60 emission thus limiting the delivered energy at the target [22-24]. Salomir et al. [25] inserted anechoic reflective

61 strips in front of the ribs. Ramaekers et al. [26] designed Voronoi-tessellated transducers based on Fermat's
62 spiral and simulated the acoustic field to calculate the near field energy deposition and the exposure energy in
63 the ribs. Very recently, Lorton et al. [15, 27] presented a new concept of transcostal HIFU transducer able to
64 thermally ablate *in vivo* deep-seated targets of pig livers. The phased array transducer composed of 256
65 hexagonal elements is designed to avoid symmetries and to have a large acoustic window for wide energy
66 distribution. The feasibility and targeting accuracy of tumor ablation located in regions considered as
67 challenging to resect was demonstrated using histologic markers in 6 pig livers. A tumor-mimicking marker
68 visible on pre-operative MR images and post-mortem gross pathology was created by a radiologist under
69 ultrasound (US) guidance. The marker was used as target for the MRgHIFU liver ablation and the planned
70 location was compared to the effective thermal ablation for accuracy assessment. The study reported 5 thermal
71 ablations confirmed on post-mortem gross pathology with a 2.4 +- 2.0 mm targeting accuracy. The measured
72 temperature on the target reached 58-86°C spatial average in a 8-mm diameter region of interest (ROI), and
73 locally exceeded 100°C in 3 pig livers, inducing a 'boiling core' [15, 28]. The authors also reported a safe ratio
74 between the temperature elevation at the target versus the ribs, in average 7.3. No specific means of protection
75 were needed for the ribs because only minor thermal lesions were noticed on MRI follow up at 7 days after the
76 intervention without any evidence on gross pathology, but a reflective layer was mandatory for the sternum.
77 Despite the validation of relevant transcostal MRgHIFU ablation in deep-seated targets, a weakness of that
78 study was the manual adjustment of the transducer position in front of the abdominal wall, with successive
79 visual check points and re-acquisition of 3D MR datasets. Besides being time consuming, this approach does
80 not guarantee the optimal position of the applicator with respect to the near field safety. Here, we are suggesting
81 computer-aided approaches in order to increase the ratio of emitted energy versus deposited energy at the focal
82 point, while reducing the intra-operative time.

83 To summarize the problem, the main issue in HIFU liver ablation is to find the best entry window which
84 minimizes the energy depletion and heating on the beam pathway, while maximizing the amount of energy
85 effectively delivered at the target.

86 Some theoretical considerations can be inferred from the skull issue which has been already investigated in
87 the context of the HIFU therapy in brain. A method based on the minimization of the average reflection
88 coefficient (ARC) was developed to find the optimal transducer position of a single-element transducer [29].

89 The technique was validated by computing acoustic simulations and the ARC algorithm required only 0.08%
90 of the total runtime of the acoustic simulation. Another way is to use the inverse problem to calculate all the
91 possible positions for the transducer by computing the phase distribution from a target point [30]. This technique
92 leads to the best transducer position but requires high computational power. In 2022, Park et al. [31] also
93 proposed a numerical optimization for finding the optimal transducer position based on time-reversal
94 simulations using the target as ultrasound source. However, the prescribed lesion shape may significantly impact
95 the optimal position, and the simulation accuracy may vary when using other frequencies, leading to spreading
96 of results. Overall, transskull HIFU sonication has the advantage of a near hemispherical entry window, while
97 transcostal HIFU sonication only exploits a limited solid angle.

98 In this paper, we present a novel software tool developed to automatically optimize the transducer
99 positioning, thereby decreasing the duration of the treatment and enhancing the thermal deposition at the target.
100 To the best of our knowledge, this is the first paper describing a method for transducer positioning in an organ
101 other than the brain. The aim of this software is to find the optimal entry window for the transducer, based on
102 the segmentation of 3D MR images, and to suggest a theoretical optimal positioning (TOP) of the device using
103 the particle swarm optimization (PSO) [32]. The software was used on retrospective data of MRgHIFU ablations
104 of *in vivo* pig livers to evaluate the applicability and relevance.

105 2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

106 2.1. Design of the transducer

107 The device is a phased array transducer dedicated to transcostal liver ablation [15, 27] (Imasonic, Voray-sur-
108 l'Ognon, France). It is composed of 256 individually controllable piezo-electric components working at 650kHz
109 and powered by a 256-channel beam former (Image Guided Therapy, Pessac, France). The transducer is
110 populated with elements widely distributed on 5 concentric segments of spheres of different radii (100, 111 and
111 124 mm) to increase the contact surface with the skin while guaranteeing a natural focal point at 10cm-depth
112 (Figure 1,a). The irregular hexagonal shape of the elements minimizes redundancies and symmetries, reduces
113 the intensity of acoustic secondary lobes and allows electronic beam steering in a $27 \times 46 \times 50 \text{ mm}^3$ volume,

114 respectively along the short axis of the transducer (x), the long axis (y) and the acoustic axis of the transducer
115 (z, see Figure 1,b).

116 The transducer is covered by a biocompatible membrane for the circulation of water between the transducer's
117 surface and the skin. A vacuum pump ensures the circulation of deionized and cooled water for the acoustic
118 coupling and active cooling of the transducer and the body. The volume of water is tunable as needed to regulate
119 the distance between the skin and the transducer for focal depth adjustments beyond the electronic displacement.
120 Eight sharp features have been defined on the computer-aided design (CAD) (Figure 1,a) enabling further
121 registration on the 3D MR images.

Figure 1. a) 3D computer-aided design of the transducer showing the 5 concentric parts of sphere. The red dots correspond to the eight markers.

b) Rear view of the 256 individual emitters populating the phased-array transducer.

122 **2.2. Software design**

123 The software was designed to optimize the transducer's position relative to the patient anatomy and target
124 location, by minimizing a cost function using the PSO algorithm. High-resolution 3D MR images (0.8 mm x
125 1.1 mm x 1.4 mm) of 5 pigs which had received an MRgHIFU liver ablation were retrospectively used and first
126 imported on into free open-source software 3D slicer [33] for segmentation. The segmentation of different

127 tissues and structures was manually performed for the attribution of the corresponding acoustic impedance,
128 including the bones, the vessels, the lungs, the liver, soft tissues, the acoustic coupling and cooling layer, the air
129 and a target mimicking a tumor (see Figure 2). The 3D volumes based on segmentations were then imported
130 into custom-made software for the optimization of the entry window. The CAD of the transducer containing the
131 centre of mass of each individual piezo-electric component was also imported into the optimization software
132 for the calculation of the cost function. After setting initial parameters (detailed in a dedicated section below),
133 the software minimized the specific cost function using the PSO and displayed the coordinates of the TOP along
134 the chosen degrees of freedom (DoF), as well as the 3D representation.

135 Various DoF can be considered for the mechanical displacement of the HIFU applicator, for instance cranio-
136 caudal translation, the radial distance from the skin to the applicator, the applicator rotation around the cranio-
137 caudal axis, or the applicator rotation around the antero-posterior axis. Here, we identified the most relevant
138 two DoF as 1) the radial distance from the skin to the applicator, and 2) the applicator rotation around the cranio-
139 caudal axis. To reduce the complexity of the problem, the applicator was considered symmetrically aligned on
140 the anatomic axial plan crossing the target.

141 The retrospective *in vivo* MR data and setup were finally used to compare the EP and the TOP and to
142 assess the relevance of this tool.

Figure 2. Segmentation of the different tissues and structures on high resolution 3D MR images using 3D slicer on the a) axial, b) sagittal and c) coronal planes. d) 3D representation of the segmentation. 1. HIFU transducer, 2. Acoustic coupling, 3. Soft tissues, 4. Liver, 5. Lungs, 6. Vessels, 7. Bones, 8. HIFU lesion.

143 **2.3. Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO)**

144 The PSO algorithm [32] consists in generating a swarm of potential solutions, called particles, able to move
 145 in a search space with speed and velocity. They iteratively move according to their own best-known position,
 146 and the entire swarm's best-known position, to converge to an optimized solution. In our specific case, the TOP
 147 is the best achievable, patient-specific, position of the transducer for liver ablation with minimized risks of bone
 148 heating. Figure 3 shows the PSO applicable to our problematic.

149
150
151
152
153
154
155
156
157
158
159
160
161
162
163
164
165
166
167
168
169
170
171
172
173
174
175
176

Figure 3. a) Chart of the PSO algorithm used to find the TOP. b) 3D volume of the segmentation of the body and of the bones lying on the CAD of the transducer. The cone-beam targeting is represented by the white dotted lines. c) Augmented reality of the transducer on a T1-weighted MR image of the pig in axial plane merged with the segmented bones (blue ROIs). The yellow dotted lines indicate the path from a transducer element to the target and the weight involved in the calculation of the cost function.

The different steps of the PSO algorithm are:

1. **Start:** The algorithm begins. The segmented 3D anatomy and the coordinates of the target are loaded, as well as the CAD of the HIFU applicator including the coordinates of the 256 individual emitters.

177 2. **Initialize Particles:** The particles, which represent potential solutions in the abstract space of
178 transducer positions and correspond to distances and angles in the physical space, are initialized
179 with random positions and velocities. Accordingly, each of the 256 acoustic elements are placed in
180 the physical space. The particles are generated in a space around the initial position of the transducer
181 defined by a rotation and a distance (see below).

182 3. **Compute cost:** The cost of each particle is calculated based on a formula defined by the user.
183 It consists of several modifiable terms adapted to the intrinsic design of the transducer that should
184 be minimized. For each acoustic element ($i=1:N$, here $N = 256$), a straight ray is defined from the
185 center of the element to the target to check which tissues are on the path and whether the constraints
186 defined by the user are respected (Figure 3, b and c). For our use, the first and critical constraint for
187 the positioning is the physical impossibility to place an acoustic element inside the patient's body.
188 The term 'elementIsInsideSurface' quantifies the number of elements inside the patient's body
189 which is weighted according to its criticality. The second constraint is the presence of bones on the
190 beam path, which is not critical but should still be minimized. The third, also noncritical, constraint
191 that should be minimized is the transducer's distance to the surface which translates into lower
192 acoustic intensity on the rib cage. The cost function is defined as follow:

$$\begin{aligned} & w_1 \cdot \text{elementIsInsideSurface}(i) \\ & + \\ 193 \quad \text{cost} = \sum_{i=1}^N w_2 \cdot \text{isBoneInUltrasoundPath}(i) & \quad [1] \\ & + \\ & w_3 \cdot \text{distanceToSurface}(i) \end{aligned}$$

194 Each term was weighted by a preset value (w_1, w_2, w_3) depending on their criticality, as defined
195 below. A schematic example of the weights involved in the calculation of the cost function is
196 available in Figure 3,c.

197 4. **Convergence check point:** The algorithm checks if it has converged, i.e. if the solution has
198 stopped improving or if a maximum number of iterations has been reached.

199 5. **Update Particles:** If the algorithm has not converged, the positions and velocities of the
200 particles are updated based on their individual best and the global best, as follows:

201
$$v_{t+1}^i = w \cdot v_t^i + c_1 \cdot r_1 \cdot (b_t^i - p_t^i) + c_2 \cdot r_2 \cdot (b_t^G - p_t^G) \quad [2]$$

202
$$p_{t+1}^i = p_t^i + v_{t+1}^i \quad [3]$$

203 In these equations, v^i represents the velocity of the i^{th} particle, p^i is the current position of the i^{th}
 204 particle, b^i is the personal best position of the i^{th} particle, and b^G is the global best position among
 205 all particles. Iteratively, the particles will then converge to the minimal value. The parameters w ,
 206 c_1 , and c_2 are constants representing inertia weight, cognitive learning factor, and social learning
 207 factor, respectively. The weight was set at 1 in order to avoid getting stuck in a local minimum.
 208 The cognitive factor c_1 represents the influence of each particle's best position it has encountered
 209 so far, and the social factor c_2 represents the influence of best position found by any particle in the
 210 swarm. We have assigned the values of 1 to both c_1 and c_2 to ensure that the cognitive and social
 211 factors carry equal weight. The r_1 and r_2 are random numbers between 0 and 1 updated at each
 212 iteration which contribute to the heuristic nature of the algorithm.

213 The velocity update equation is responsible for adjusting the particle's velocity, considering the
 214 particle's previous velocity ($w \cdot v^i$), the cognitive component that directs the particle towards its
 215 individual best position ($c_1 \cdot r_1 \cdot (b_t^i - p_t^i)$), and the social component that directs the particle
 216 towards the global best position ($c_2 \cdot r_2 \cdot (b_t^G - p_t^G)$).

217 The position update equation adds the updated velocity to the particle's current position at iteration
 218 “ t ”, thereby moving the particle to a new position at iteration “ $t+1$ ” in the search space. The
 219 algorithm then goes back to step 3 until convergence or the maximum number of iterations.

220 6. **Stop:** The algorithm concludes and returns the best solution found once it has converged. In this
 221 study, convergence was determined by reaching a maximum number of iterations, specifically set
 222 at 20 based on our experience after extensive testing of the algorithm.

223 7. **Repeat the PSO algorithm:** To mitigate the risk of converging to a local minimum, the PSO
 224 algorithm was executed three times. This repetition enhances the robustness of the solution by
 225 providing multiple opportunities to explore the search space and potentially discover a more optimal
 226 solution.

227 As a result, the software provides the relative transform between the current segmented transducer's position
228 and the optimally computed placement.

229 **2.4. Weighting factors of the cost function**

230 The simplicity of having only two DoF to optimize in our cost function enables us to represent this cost as a 2D
231 heatmap for analysis purpose, providing a visual understanding of each component's contribution. In the
232 ensuing analysis, we offer a visual depiction of the unique and combined effects of various cost function
233 components within our PSO algorithm. Each part of Figure 4 represents a different cost function component for
234 a single pig, illustrating its distinct contribution to the overall cost calculation. The final part integrates all three
235 components, demonstrating the collective effect when all weights are uniformly set to 1/3.

Figure 4. Heatmaps of each cost component and their balanced combination of weights $(\frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{3})$, as a function of two independent DoF, here the distance to skin and the rotation angle around the cranio-caudal axis. Darker pixels indicate lower cost, hence better coordinate of the HIFU applicator. (a) Cost heatmap representing the influence of the 'Inside Body' component. (b) Cost heatmap detailing the effect of the 'Bones in Path' component. (c) Cost heatmap showcasing the impact of the 'Distance from Element to Skin' component. (d) Heatmap displaying the combined costs with equal contributions from each component.

236 The PSO algorithm aims to minimize the cost, with the black regions in the heatmaps indicating the minimum
 237 regions. These black areas provide a visual representation of the regions where the algorithm is likely to
 238 converge.

239 The weighting of each cost component is certainly open to discussion. We initially know that w_1 , representing
 240 the "Inside Body" component, is the most critical since we want to forbid the transducer from entering the body,
 241 meaning this weight should be high. We opted for the combination $w_1=3/6$, $w_2=2/6$, $w_3=1/6$ based on the
 242 prioritization of the cost function components. The highest importance was given to "Inside Body", ensuring
 243 the transducer doesn't enter the body, followed by the "Bones in Path" and the "Distance to surface"
 244 components, respectively.

Figure 5. Display of the global cost function using various component weights showing the significance of the weighting. w_1 represents the "Inside Body" component, w_2 represents the "Bones in Path" component, and w_3 represents the "Distance from Element to Skin" component. (a) Heatmap with weight configuration $w_1=2/5$, $w_2=1/5$, $w_3=2/5$. (b) Heatmap with weight configuration $w_1=3/6$, $w_2=2/6$, $w_3=1/6$. (c) Heatmap with weight configuration $w_1=3/6$, $w_2=1/6$, $w_3=2/6$. (d) Heatmap with weight configuration $w_1=2/4$, $w_2=1/4$, $w_3=1/4$.

245

246 2.5. Initial parameters

247 Here, the transducer's main z-axis, shown in Figure 1.b, is set parallel to the anatomic axial plane and is
 248 crossing the target with pinpoint accuracy. The TOP is defined in a coordinate system that includes rotation
 249 around the cranio-caudal axis in trigonometric degrees and radial distance to the target in
 250 millimeters. Furthermore, the transducer is positioned outside the body at a default distance of 10cm from the
 251 target, which corresponds to its natural focal length. This alignment serves as the starting point for the PSO
 252 algorithm, setting the stage for further optimization.

253 Particles are initialized within a search area surrounding this initial transducer position, within an acceptable
 254 range in terms of physical implementation. The range of tested positions is confined within a span of $[-40^\circ,$
 255 $40^\circ]$ for rotation, as the holding system of the transducer is technically limited to this interval. The range for
 256 varying the distance to the target was set to $[-20, 20]$ mm as this corresponds to the electronic beam capacities

257 of the transducer along the z-axis. These ranges provide a comprehensive yet focused search space for the PSO
258 algorithm to explore and identify the optimal transducer placement. The number of particles was empirically
259 determined to be 20, and the iteration limit was set at 20, as the algorithm commonly reached a plateau by the
260 10th iteration. Further iterations beyond this point yielded only marginal improvements to the cost function. To
261 mitigate the risk of converging to local minima due to the non-continuous nature of the cost function, the
262 algorithm was executed three times. We therefore considered adequate the number of iterations as double that
263 needed to reach the plateau.

264 2.6. Software Implementation

265 The software was developed and tested on a commonly available consumer-grade computer equipped with
266 an Intel Core i7-8550U processor, 16GB of RAM, and running Ubuntu 22.04 LTS. The implementation uses
267 Python 3.10 and incorporates VTK 9.2.6 for visualization and ITK 5.3.0 for image processing. The software
268 includes a Graphical User Interface (GUI) and a 3D viewer that allows easy visualization of the segmented
269 body, the target tumor and the transducer position (Figure 6). It also provides the flexibility to set different
270 optimization and initial parameters, such as the coordinates of the transducer, the search area, or the weight of
271 each variable.

Figure 6: Graphical user interface of the software showing the 3D reconstruction of the segmented body lying on the transducer and the functionalities of the software.

272 **2.7. Evaluation**

273 The relevancy of the software was validated by comparing the TOP to the experimental position (EP) of the
274 transducer during an MRgHIFU ablation of 5 pig livers. The EP was manually determined through a time-
275 consuming iterative process performed by interventional MRI experts. The EP iterative process consisted of
276 roughly placing the transducer, acquiring high-resolution (HR) 3D MR images, controlling the entry window,
277 the targeting or the presence of bones, measuring the correction to apply to the transducer position, re-
278 positioning the device and repeating this cycle until the MR images indicated a satisfactory position for our
279 HIFU experts on site. Our software addresses this positioning issue by providing computational insights to
280 accurately identify the TOP, eliminating the need for repetitive trial-and-error approaches. To this aim, high
281 resolution 3D T1-weighted MR images of 5 pig abdomens *in vivo* were acquired on a 3T MR scanner (Prisma
282 Fit, Siemens Healthineers, Erlangen,) using the following parameters: acquisition time = 54 s, repetition time
283 = 4.08 ms, first and second echo times for Dixon reconstruction of 1.35 ms and 2.58 ms, respectively, flip angle
284 (FA) = 9.5°, bandwidth = 1040 Hz/pixel, acquisition resolution = $0.8 \times 1.1 \times 1.4 \text{ mm}^3$, reconstruction resolution
285 = $0.8 \times 0.8 \times 1.2 \text{ mm}^3$, number of slices = 112, slice oversampling 30% and parallel imaging GRAPPA = 2. The
286 MR images were imported into 3D Slicer and the different tissue types were manually segmented. It should be
287 noted that the HIFU transducer does not provide signal in MR images and the indirect segmentation of the water
288 compartment in front of it does not guarantees sufficient accuracy. Therefore, to retrieve the EP of the transducer
289 and register it with the 3D volume-based segmentations of the pig abdomens, the CAD of the transducer
290 engineering was exploited. An expert user pointed out in the 3D MR dataset the four corners of the transducer
291 central segment, and the four corners of the second segments that are indicated in Figure 1a as red dots. Their
292 rigid coordinates are known a priori from the transduced engineering process. The software computed the cost
293 functions of the theoretical and the experimental positions and displayed the two positions in the GUI. It also
294 indicated the difference of the TOP compared to the EP using two DoF: along the depth axis of the transducer,
295 meaning a compression or a distance to the skin, and a rotation around the cranio-caudal direction. For
296 evaluation purpose, an exhaustive heatmap of the cost function for the TOP was computed every 1mm of depth
297 and every 1° of rotation for each of the 5 pigs. The minimum TOP cost function was compared to the EP cost

298 function to quantify their difference. The robustness and consistency of the software was evaluated by repeating
299 50 times the PSO algorithm on each of the 5 pigs to conclude on the accuracy.

300 3. RESULTS

301 During the validation process conducted on five pigs, the mapping of the cost function with two DoF, across
302 80 rotations and 40 distances took a constant time of 115s and the computing time for the TOP using the PSO
303 algorithm lasted 20s. This result is promising for real-time application intra-operatory.

304 The cost mapping, as illustrated in Figure 7, revealed a monomodal form of the graph for the weight
305 combination (1/2, 1/3, 1/6) leading to a unique optimal position or nearly optimal position. While these
306 convergence points are not identical, their close proximity to each other — evidenced by a standard deviation
307 of 1.5 degrees and 0.4 mm, and a maximum spread of 5.5 degrees and 2.2 mm — indicates a high degree of
308 similarity in position. This reflects the robustness of the algorithm in consistently identifying near-optimal
309 solutions within the defined search space.

c

Figure 7. a) Displayed result after minimizing the cost function. The 3D representation of the segmented body lying on the CAD drawing of the transducer in the EOP (deep blue) is superimposed with the TOP (light blue). b) Accuracy heatmap for Fig 4: This heatmap records the final best positions obtained from 50 repeated runs of the PSO algorithm, using the default search space, to evaluate the algorithm's consistency and precision. c) Robustness of convergence: This panel illustrates the results of 50 repeated runs of the PSO algorithm, within an expanded search space deliberately centered far from the optimal position. d) Single PSO run analysis: This figure presents the best solutions for individual particles as well as the overall best solution found in a single PSO run.

310 Compared to the EP, the TOP optimized the rib cage and the software computed the mismatch of the TOP
 311 compared to the EP. The differences in the 5 pigs are presented in Table 2:

312 **Table 2. Differences between the TOP and the EP using two DoF .**

Pig	Differences between the (° trigonometric, mm)	Difference between the costs of the TOP and the EP, normalized to the maximum cost in the search space
1	10.2°/-7.3 mm	0.06
2	-12°/-7.0mm	0.11
3	-0.2°/-15.8mm	0.08
4	-4.4°/-8.0mm	0.09
5	-9.1°/2.8mm	0.04

313 The theoretical approach angles were similar to the experimental ones; however, the transducer during
314 experiments was more distant to the skin compared to the computed one. The rotation correction to apply was
315 on average $-3.1 \pm 7.1^\circ$ ($-12^\circ - 10.2^\circ$) and the distance correction was on average $-7.1 \pm 5.4\text{mm}$ ($-15.8 - 2.8\text{mm}$).
316 As demonstrated in Figure 7,c, the consistent convergence of the algorithm to a similar region after 50
317 repetitions, even when initiated from significantly different starting points, underscores the robustness of our
318 method and reliability of our approach in various scenarios.

319 **4. Discussion**

320 The optimization software was designed user-friendly with real-time and interactive visualization of the 3D
321 segmentations and the CAD drawing of the transducer. The iterative process for the position calculation was
322 fast, with a computing duration not exceeding 20s, and could be significantly speed-up with parallel computing,
323 which is compatible with intra-operatory execution. Nevertheless, the manual segmentation time of around 40
324 minutes should be considered in the total procedure time. The use of the software could drastically reduce the
325 installation duration for an MRgHIFU ablation, as until now the targeting and positioning was an iterative
326 process between the MR measurements and the manual adjustments, that took 1-2h per session.

327 For the establishment of heatmaps, the range for the distance to the target was set to ± 20 mm to stay within
328 the steering capacities of the transducer. Wherever the TOP is in the authorized range, the focal point should be
329 electronically adjusted to shoot the target, and during positioning, the volume under the membrane needs to be
330 tuned up to compensate for the transducer moving closer or further away, without losing acoustic coupling. A
331 tumor that is too superficial or too profound is intrinsically inaccessible with this transducer anyway. The target
332 should be located at least 2cm into the liver, which corresponds approximately to 4cm from the skin in a person
333 of average build.

334 The similarity between the TOP and the EP is a strong argument of the algorithm's efficacy, robustness and
335 reliability. Lower cost functions in TOP even suggest that the EP could have been slightly optimized.

336 In normal use after validation, determining the TOP necessitates the iterative computation of the best
337 coordinates of the transducer position in the space of configurations. The exhaustive heatmap, which represents
338 the dense mapping of the cost function, was primarily included in the article for illustrative and validation

339 purposes. This visualization provides insights into how each component of the cost function influences the
340 overall calculation. The mapping of the cost function was useful during the validation process to confirm the
341 unique TOP, and analyze the evolution of the cost function with various weights, however the software does
342 not intend to compute this mapping for daily use. The only output for the clinician is the coordinates of the TOP
343 based on the PSO algorithm. Mapping the cost function with additional DoF in a higher dimension space of
344 configurations would drastically increase the computation time.

345 The software demonstrated consistency and accuracy, supported by the suggestion of similar TOP when
346 repeating the algorithm (see Figure 7, b). The random generation of particles by the PSO algorithm may explain
347 the small differences in the suggested position because of the falling of the particles to a local minimum. The
348 probability of staying in a local minimum is drastically lowered by the attribution of high speed and inertia of
349 each particle but may still occur. Repetition of the algorithm further helped avoiding this issue.

350 The program is modifiable and easily adjustable to other constraints and tissue features. The starting point
351 and initialization settings can be changed to fit other transducers, widening the indications and the targeted
352 organs, such as bone metastases or prostate. The use may be extended to other purposes, such as proposing a
353 personalized virtual planning before the intervention to assess the feasibility or the compliance with inclusion
354 criteria. The software may be able to calculate an eligibility score based on anatomical criteria to help the
355 clinician in the inclusion process. For liver ablation, the software may also be used for the reflective patch
356 positioned in front of the sternum, as described by Lorton et al. [15, 27] to avoid thermal effects, and could be
357 extended to propose a position or a correction for the sternum protector.

358 The EP distance to the skin mostly exceeded the retrospectively TOP calculated one. This could be
359 explained by the experimental learning curve. The closer the transducer to the skin, the lower the risk of inducing
360 thermal effects on the ribs, but the realization of the physical setup becomes more difficult. The software has
361 been updated with this information to find the optimal distance by minimizing the distance to the skin, but still
362 considering the need to keep a cooling and coupling layer between the skin and the transducer surface.

363 It is important to note that while the cost function may show slight improvements with additional iterations,
364 the corresponding changes in rotation and translation are so minute that they are practically irrelevant, that is,
365 the numerical precision of the algorithm exceeds the physical accuracy achievable for the transducer positioning
366 in a therapeutic scenario.

367 While the software is valuable and of great interest to help the interventional team to place the transducer
368 for MRgHIFU ablation of the liver, it currently requires manual segmentation of structures such as bones, soft
369 tissues and target as input, which is time-consuming. The segmentations also have to be performed on
370 radiological software and exported in the right format. Future improvements will focus on developing tools to
371 automate this segmentation process, further reducing the time required for optimal transducer placement and
372 enabling its prospective use intra-operatory. This study lacks data on the potential clinical improvement between
373 the EP versus the TOP positioning, for instance in term of the thermal heating ratio at the target versus the ribs.
374 The purpose of this paper was to present the novel concept of HIFU transducer's TOP computing.

375 Another improvement would be the addition of more DoF for the transducer positioning. This study only
376 considered rotation around the cranio-caudal axis and the distance to the skin, while rotation around the z axis
377 of the transducer or translation along the cranio-caudal direction could be included for instance. Furthermore,
378 the precision of the positioning could be improved by computing a more elaborated cost function with additional
379 terms in Equation [1] that would be assigned with lower weights. For instance, the presence of the lungs or the
380 stomach on the beam path or an angle to avoid focusing through a major blood vessel could be considered to
381 proceed to fine adjustments of the positioning.

382 **5. Conclusion**

383 The developed software tool is suggested to significantly support the optimization of transducer placement for
384 abdominal HIFU treatments. By automating a previously manual and time-consuming process, it has the
385 potential to significantly reduce treatment time and increase patient comfort while maximizing the ratio of
386 energy deposited versus energy emitted. The suggested software is modifiable, and the research of the optimal
387 position is consistent. Future improvements would be focused on further automating the process of segmentation
388 to provide better care for patients.

389

390

391 **Acknowledgements**

392 The authors thank Mr John Diaper, Mrs Sylvie Roulet, Mr Xavier Belin, Mrs Fabienne Fontao and Prof. Dr.
393 Walid Habre for the animal preparation and care. The authors also thank the Center of Biomedical Imaging
394 (CIBM) for providing access to the MR scanner and the Imasonic company (Voray sur l'Ognon, France) for the
395 state-of-the-art manufacturing of the transducer. The 'Centre des affections hépato-biliaires et pancréatiques' of
396 the University Hospitals of Geneva is acknowledged for supporting in-house software development.

397

398 **Statements of ethical approval**

399 The animal study was reviewed and approved by the Animal Research Committee of Geneva Canton, under the
400 reference GE/95/20.

401

402 **Funding**

403 This study was funded by the Swiss National Foundation of Science (320030_185308).

404

405 **Disclosure**

406 The author reports no conflicts of interest in this work.

407

408 **References**

- 409 [1] B. D. de Senneville, C. Mougenot, B. Quesson, I. Dragonu, N. Grenier, and C. T. Moonen, "MR
410 thermometry for monitoring tumor ablation," *Eur Radiol*, vol. 17, no. 9, pp. 2401-10, Sep 2007, doi:
411 10.1007/s00330-007-0646-6.
- 412 [2] K. Kuroda, "MR techniques for guiding high-intensity focused ultrasound (HIFU) treatments," *J Magn
413 Reson Imaging*, vol. 47, no. 2, pp. 316-331, Feb 2018, doi: 10.1002/jmri.25770.
- 414 [3] N. McDannold, "Quantitative MRI-based temperature mapping based on the proton resonant
415 frequency shift: review of validation studies," *Int J Hyperthermia*, vol. 21, no. 6, pp. 533-46, Sep 2005,
416 doi: 10.1080/02656730500096073.
- 417 [4] Y. Ishihara *et al.*, "A precise and fast temperature mapping using water proton chemical shift," *Magn
418 Reson Med*, vol. 34, no. 6, pp. 814-23, Dec 1995, doi: 10.1002/mrm.1910340606.
- 419 [5] L. Drost *et al.*, "Ultrasound-Guided Focused Ultrasound Treatment for Painful Bone Metastases: A Pilot
420 Study," *Ultrasound Med Biol*, vol. 46, no. 6, pp. 1455-1463, Jun 2020, doi:
421 10.1016/j.ultrasmedbio.2020.01.032.
- 422 [6] J. Hindley *et al.*, "MRI guidance of focused ultrasound therapy of uterine fibroids: early results," *AJR
423 Am J Roentgenol*, vol. 183, no. 6, pp. 1713-9, Dec 2004, doi: 10.2214/ajr.183.6.01831713.
- 424 [7] A. Napoli *et al.*, "Focused Ultrasound and External Beam Radiation Therapy for Painful Bone
425 Metastases: A Phase II Clinical Trial," *Radiology*, vol. 307, no. 2, p. e211857, Apr 2023, doi:
426 10.1148/radiol.211857.

- 427 [8] H. U. Ahmed *et al.*, "High-intensity-focused ultrasound in the treatment of primary prostate cancer:
428 the first UK series," *Br J Cancer*, vol. 101, no. 1, pp. 19-26, Jul 7 2009, doi: 10.1038/sj.bjc.6605116.
- 429 [9] A. Napoli *et al.*, "Real-time magnetic resonance-guided high-intensity focused ultrasound focal
430 therapy for localised prostate cancer: preliminary experience," *Eur Urol*, vol. 63, no. 2, pp. 395-8, Feb
431 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.eururo.2012.11.002.
- 432 [10] Y. Ji *et al.*, "High-intensity focused ultrasound (HIFU) treatment for uterine fibroids: a meta-analysis,"
433 *Arch Gynecol Obstet*, vol. 296, no. 6, pp. 1181-1188, Dec 2017, doi: 10.1007/s00404-017-4548-9.
- 434 [11] L. Poissonnier *et al.*, "Control of prostate cancer by transrectal HIFU in 227 patients," *Eur Urol*, vol. 51,
435 no. 2, pp. 381-7, Feb 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.eururo.2006.04.012.
- 436 [12] W. J. Wang, H. L. Lee, S. C. Jeng, J. F. Chiou, and Y. Huang, "Real-Time Magnetic Resonance Guided
437 Focused Ultrasound for Painful Bone Metastases," *J Vis Exp*, no. 169, Mar 5 2021, doi: 10.3791/60615.
- 438 [13] E. K. Abdalla, R. Adam, A. J. Bilchik, D. Jaeck, J. N. Vauthey, and D. Mahvi, "Improving resectability of
439 hepatic colorectal metastases: expert consensus statement," *Ann Surg Oncol*, vol. 13, no. 10, pp. 1271-
440 80, Oct 2006, doi: 10.1245/s10434-006-9045-5.
- 441 [14] R. Stangl, A. Altendorf-Hofmann, R. M. Charnley, and J. Scheele, "Factors influencing the natural
442 history of colorectal liver metastases," *Lancet*, vol. 343, no. 8910, pp. 1405-10, Jun 4 1994, doi:
443 10.1016/s0140-6736(94)92529-1.
- 444 [15] O. Lorton *et al.*, "In Vivo Thermal Ablation of Deep Intrahepatic Targets Using a Super-Convergent
445 MRgHIFU Applicator and a Pseudo-Tumor Model," *Cancers (Basel)*, vol. 15, no. 15, Aug 3 2023, doi:
446 10.3390/cancers15153961.
- 447 [16] B. Martin and J. H. McElhane, "The acoustic properties of human skull bone," *J Biomed Mater Res*,
448 vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 325-33, Jul 1971, doi: 10.1002/jbm.820050405.
- 449 [17] G. Pinton, J. F. Aubry, E. Bossy, M. Muller, M. Pernot, and M. Tanter, "Attenuation, scattering, and
450 absorption of ultrasound in the skull bone," *Med Phys*, vol. 39, no. 1, pp. 299-307, Jan 2012, doi:
451 10.1118/1.3668316.
- 452 [18] "National Council of Radiation Protection (NCRP). National council of radiation protection &
453 measurements report no.74: Biological effects of ultrasound: Mechanisms and clinical implications
454 (report no. 74)." *Technical report, NCRP.*, 1983.
- 455 [19] M. Anzidei *et al.*, "Magnetic resonance-guided focused ultrasound ablation in abdominal moving
456 organs: a feasibility study in selected cases of pancreatic and liver cancer," *Cardiovasc Intervent Radiol*,
457 vol. 37, no. 6, pp. 1611-7, Dec 2014, doi: 10.1007/s00270-014-0861-x.
- 458 [20] F. Wu *et al.*, "Extracorporeal high intensity focused ultrasound ablation in the treatment of patients
459 with large hepatocellular carcinoma," *Ann Surg Oncol*, vol. 11, no. 12, pp. 1061-9, Dec 2004, doi:
460 10.1245/ASO.2004.02.026.
- 461 [21] H. Zhu *et al.*, "High intensity focused ultrasound (HIFU) therapy for local treatment of hepatocellular
462 carcinoma: role of partial rib resection," *Eur J Radiol*, vol. 72, no. 1, pp. 160-6, Oct 2009, doi:
463 10.1016/j.ejrad.2008.07.003.
- 464 [22] B. Quesson *et al.*, "Real-time volumetric MRI thermometry of focused ultrasound ablation in vivo: a
465 feasibility study in pig liver and kidney," *NMR Biomed*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 145-53, Feb 2011, doi:
466 10.1002/nbm.1563.
- 467 [23] M. Zubair and R. Dickinson, "Calculating the Effect of Ribs on the Focus Quality of a Therapeutic
468 Spherical Random Phased Array," *Sensors (Basel)*, vol. 21, no. 4, Feb 9 2021, doi: 10.3390/s21041211.
- 469 [24] D. McMahon and M. Almekkawy, "Elements Selection for Transcostal HIFU Refocusing Method:
470 Simulation Study," *IEEE Trans Ultrason Ferroelectr Freq Control*, vol. 67, no. 7, pp. 1366-1376, Jul 2020,
471 doi: 10.1109/TUFFC.2020.2973678.
- 472 [25] R. Salomir *et al.*, "Magnetic resonance-guided shielding of prefocal acoustic obstacles in focused
473 ultrasound therapy: application to intercostal ablation in liver," *Invest Radiol*, vol. 48, no. 6, pp. 366-
474 80, Jun 2013, doi: 10.1097/RLI.0b013e31827a90d7.
- 475 [26] P. Ramaekers, M. Ries, C. T. Moonen, and M. de Greef, "Improved intercostal HIFU ablation using a
476 phased array transducer based on Fermat's spiral and Voronoi tessellation: A numerical evaluation,"
477 *Med Phys*, vol. 44, no. 3, pp. 1071-1088, Mar 2017, doi: 10.1002/mp.12082.

- 478 [27] O. Lorton *et al.*, "A Novel Concept of a Phased-Array HIFU Transducer Optimized for MR-Guided
479 Hepatic Ablation: Embodiment and First In-Vivo Studies," *Front Oncol*, vol. 12, p. 899440, 2022, doi:
480 10.3389/fonc.2022.899440.
- 481 [28] M. Viallon *et al.*, "Experimental methods for improved spatial control of thermal lesions in magnetic
482 resonance-guided focused ultrasound ablation," *Ultrasound Med Biol*, vol. 39, no. 9, pp. 1580-95, Sep
483 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.ultrasmedbio.2013.03.018.
- 484 [29] T. Y. Park, K. J. Pahk, and H. Kim, "Method to optimize the placement of a single-element transducer
485 for transcranial focused ultrasound," *Comput Methods Programs Biomed*, vol. 179, p. 104982, Oct
486 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.cmpb.2019.104982.
- 487 [30] M. V. Joseph Blackmore, Christopher Butler, Robin Cleveland, "Focusing ultrasound through the skull
488 for neuromodulation," *J Acoust Soc Am*, vol. 141, no. 5_Supplement, 2017.
- 489 [31] T. Y. Park, H. J. Kim, S. H. Park, W. S. Chang, H. Kim, and K. Yoon, "Differential evolution method to find
490 optimal location of a single-element transducer for transcranial focused ultrasound therapy," *Comput
491 Methods Programs Biomed*, vol. 219, p. 106777, Jun 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.cmpb.2022.106777.
- 492 [32] R. E. J. Kennedy, "Particle swarm optimization," *Proceedings of ICNN'95 - International Conference on
493 Neural Networks, Perth, WA, Australia*, vol. 4, pp. 1942-4948, 1995, doi: doi:
494 10.1109/ICNN.1995.488968.
- 495 [33] A. Fedorov *et al.*, "3D Slicer as an image computing platform for the Quantitative Imaging Network,"
496 *Magn Reson Imaging*, vol. 30, no. 9, pp. 1323-41, Nov 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.mri.2012.05.001.

497

**Computer-Aided Intra-Operatory Positioning of an MRgHIFU Applicator
dedicated to Abdominal Thermal Therapy using Particle Swarm
Optimization**

Yacine M'Rad, Caecilia Charbonnier, Marcelo Elias de Oliveira, Pauline Coralie Guillemin, Lindsey Alexandra Crowe, Thibaud Kössler, Pierre-Alexandre Poletti, Sana Boudabbous, Alexis Ricoeur, Rares Salomir, Orane Lorton

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Computer-Aided Intra-Operatory Positioning of an MRgHIFU Applicator dedicated to Abdominal Thermal Therapy using Particle Swarm Optimization

Yacine M'Rad, Caecilia Charbonnier, Marcelo Elias de Oliveira, Pauline Coralie Guillemin, Lindsey Alexandra Crowe, Thibaud Kössler, Pierre-Alexandre Poletti, Sana Boudabbous, Alexis Ricoeur, Rares Salomir, Orane Lorton

The authors declare they all contributed to the conception and design of the study, the acquisition of data, the analysis or the interpretation of data. They all participated to the writing and revision of this manuscript and approved the final version of the manuscript.